

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE PROBLEM OF INCREASING LEARNING MOTIVATION IN JUNIOR SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH THE ORGANIZATION OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE LESSONS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *Having studied the psychological and pedagogical literature, we have established that motives associated with the educational process are divided into cognitive motives associated with the content of educational activity and the process of its implementation and social motives associated with various social interactions of the student with other people. That is why the key figure in the formation of educational motivation is not only the teacher, but also the child's parents, so it is important to make them your allies in this matter, otherwise the teacher's attempts to resolve this issue will be minimized.*

Keywords: *formation, motivation, psychology, pedagogy, education, training, education, technology.*

Didactic games are associated with a game form of interaction between the teacher and students, their implementation in lessons occurs as follows: a didactic goal is set for students in the form of a game task, educational activities are subject to the rules of the game, educational material is used as its means, an element of competition is introduced into educational activities, which transforms a didactic task into a game one, thus, the use of didactic games in elementary school lessons, according to leading Russian psychologists L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev, D. B. Elkonin, really creates conditions for the formation of a positive emotional mood in a younger student, it arouses his interest in the educational work being performed, improves overall performance, and makes it possible to repeat the same educational material in different ways.

Terms and Definitions:

1. A didactic game (educational game) is a type of activity in which children learn [Elkonin D. B. "Psychology of Game"].

2. Interest (from the Latin "matter, important") is an emotional state associated with the implementation of cognitive activity and characterized by the incentive of this activity [Big Psychological Encyclopedia].

3. Junior school age is a stage in the development of a child that corresponds to the period of his education in elementary school [Chikisheva O.V. Psychological and pedagogical characteristics of children of primary school age].

4. Motive - an incentive to activity related to meeting the needs of the subject [Big Psychological Encyclopedia].

5. Educational motivation – motivated activity demonstrated by students in achieving learning goals [Zimnyaya I.A. Pedagogical psychology].

The purpose of our thesis was to study the characteristics of educational motivation of younger schoolchildren and develop lessons using didactic games that ensure its increase [4].

We believe that we have fully realized the goal set for us, since we have solved all the problems of our diploma research.

The first task of our work was to study the concept of “learning motivation” and the features of its formation in primary school age.

We have expanded on the concept of “learning motivation”, defining that it is the motivated activity exhibited by students in achieving learning goals. Educational motivation acts as a particular type of general motivation, an integral part of which is motives.

Having studied the psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue, we found that the motives associated with the educational process are divided into cognitive, which are associated with the content of educational activities and the process of its implementation, and social, associated with various social interactions of the student, therefore a key figure in the formation of the educational motivation of the younger The schoolchild is represented not only by the teacher, who is responsible for the formation of cognitive motives, but also by the parents, who are responsible for the formation of social motives for the child’s learning even in preschool age[5].

The second objective of our thesis was to study the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of primary school age.

In the psychological literature, junior school age is designated as a stage in the development of a child, which corresponds to the period of his education in primary school. The boundaries of primary school age are conventionally defined in the range from 6-7 to 10-11 years.

The leading activity at this age is educational; it is this activity that determines the most important changes that occur in the development of the psyche of children at this age stage.

Within the framework of educational activities, psychological new formations are formed that characterize the most significant achievements in the development of primary schoolchildren and are the foundation that ensures their development at subsequent age stages.

At this age, the primary schoolchild actively develops memory and attention, and the transition from visual-figurative to verbal-logical thinking that began in preschool age is completed.

At primary school age, the child is introduced to the working life of society, hard work and a taste for work are developed. For the first time, a junior schoolchild becomes, both at school and in the family, a member of a real work team, which is the main condition for the formation of his personality. Life in a team organized by the school and teacher leads to the development of complex, social feelings in the child and to the practical mastery of the most important forms and rules of social behavior [6].

The third objective of our diploma research was to characterize the main types and types of lessons in primary school according to the national curriculum.

Having analyzed the national curriculum, we found out that the development of a child’s personality is a priority task of a modern school, which requires a new approach to organizing the learning process from primary school teachers.

The lesson at the heart of the national curriculum is defined as the basic unit of the educational process, but it fundamentally changes the functionality of the teacher and the main activity of the students. The leading task of the teacher is, first of all, to help students master knowledge. The main activity in the lesson is the independent work of students; the priority approach to organizing activities is activity-based [7].

A modern lesson should be problematic in nature, starting from the goal-setting stage. The problem of the lesson should be formulated by the students themselves under the guidance of the teacher. It is necessary to discuss different points of view on emerging educational issues, find common ways to solve them, bring students to the significance of the knowledge they receive and the ability to apply it in practice.

We have described the modern typology of lessons in primary school, having analyzed the types and content of each stage of the structure of a modern lesson, we noted that the very understanding of a lesson, as part of the educational process, is completely aimed at the development of the student as an active subject of his cognitive activity[8].

The fourth objective of our diploma research was to study the concept of “Didactic game”, the features of its application in lessons in primary school.

An analysis of the literature studied allowed us to conclude that the use of didactic games in lessons in elementary school creates conditions not only for the education of younger schoolchildren, but also for their motivation for further successful educational activities.

Research by the classics of Russian and Soviet pedagogy indicates that in game activities, students’ mental actions are formed, their imaginative thinking develops, and learning motivation is formed.

We have established that a didactic game is understood as a type of activity in which children learn.

Analysis of methodological literature allowed us to determine the classification of didactic games. In the educational process of primary school, they can be divided into three groups:

1. educational (their goals are for the student to acquire new knowledge, skills, and abilities)
2. controlling (their goals are to repeat, consolidate, and test previously acquired knowledge by students)
3. generalizing (aimed at students acquiring skills to act in various learning situations, associated with integration).

Based on the work of A.Yu. Teshabayev, we found that the didactic game has a stable structure, its main components are the game concept, rules, game actions, cognitive content or didactic tasks, equipment, and the result of the game.

Thus, we can conclude that a modern lesson, unlike a traditional one, is a lesson of joint activity between the teacher and students, where the active role belongs to the student.

The main differences between a modern lesson on the national curriculum and a traditional lesson are presented in the table:

Having analyzed the types and content of each stage of the structure of a modern lesson, it should be noted that the very understanding of the lesson, as part of the educational process, is fully aimed at developing the student as an active subject of his cognitive activity, which creates all the conditions for the formation of positive motivation for the learning process already in itself, and the task of a modern primary school teacher is to effectively use a variety of forms, methods and techniques of student work in the classroom, one of which is a didactic game.

An analysis of the studied pedagogical and methodological literature allows us to conclude that didactic games can be used in any lessons in primary school, since they create conditions for the development of basic mental operations in a form that is accessible and interesting for students [9-11].

Table 1 - The main differences between a modern lesson according to the national curriculum and a traditional lesson

Lesson stages	Traditional lesson	National curriculum lesson
Announcing the topic of the lesson	The teacher himself tells the students the topic of the lesson	The topic of the lesson is formulated by the students themselves under the guidance of the teacher.
Message goals and objectives	The teacher formulates and tells students what they need to learn.	The objectives of the lesson are formulated by the students themselves, defining the boundaries of their knowledge and ignorance
Planning	The teacher tells students what work they must do in class to achieve the goal.	Planning by students themselves how to achieve their goals
Practical activities of students	Under the guidance of the teacher, students perform a series of practical tasks (the frontal method of organizing activities is more often used)	Students carry out learning activities according to the planned plan (priority is given to group and individual methods and forms of work)
Exercising control	The teacher exercises sole control over students' performance of practical work.	Students themselves exercise control over their activities (various forms of self-control and mutual control are used)
Implementation of correction	The teacher makes corrections during the implementation and based on the results of the work completed by the students.	Students independently formulate difficulties and carry out corrections independently
Student assessment	The teacher evaluates students for their work in class	Students themselves evaluate their activities based on their results (self-assessment, assessment of the results of the activities of their comrades)

Lesson summary	The teacher asks the students what they remember at the end of the lesson.	Reflection is taking place
Homework	The teacher announces and comments on one task for everyone	Students can choose tasks from those proposed by the teacher, taking into account individual capabilities

Thus, the hypothesis of our thesis research was confirmed; the use of didactic games in lessons in primary school actually helps to increase the level of educational motivation of primary schoolchildren in the 3rd grade.

The leading task of a modern primary school teacher is to help students master knowledge; he should only guide them in finding answers to educational questions. The priority in the modern lesson is the independent work of primary school students; the main approaches to organizing activities are the activity approach.

We studied the modern typology of lessons according to the national curriculum, compared the content of the stages of the traditional and modern lesson structure.

In the theoretical part of our diploma research, we also examined the concept of “Didactic game”. A didactic game is a type of activity in which children learn. We studied the classification of didactic games, examined its structure and its structural components.

Analysis of the literature studied allowed us to conclude that the use of didactic games in lessons in elementary school creates conditions not only for the learning of younger schoolchildren, but also motivates them for further successful educational activities.

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